

Moderating Role of Board Gender Diversity on Credit and Market Risks Information Disclosure and Market Value of Listed Companies in Financial Sector of Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examines the moderating role of board gender diversity on the relationship between credit and market risk information disclosure and market value of listed companies in Nigeria's financial sector. Using a Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) approach, the analysis covers a sample of 432 company-year observations. The results reveal a significant negative relationship between credit risk information disclosure and firm market value, while market risk information disclosure has a positive effect on market value. Additionally, board gender diversity moderates these relationships differently: it reduces the negative impact of credit risk information disclosure on market value but diminishes the positive effect of market risk information disclosure. The study highlights the critical role of board gender diversity in influencing how risk information is perceived by the market. Diverse boards, particularly those involving women, bring varied perspectives that improve governance and risk management, helping firms manage investors' reactions to risk information disclosures. Based on the findings, the study recommends that listed companies in the financial sector of Nigeria should increase board gender diversity by involving women, adopt balanced risk communication strategies, and leverage diverse boards for more effective governance. The results have important implications for policymakers, corporate governance practitioners, and investors, emphasizing the need for robust and transparent risk information disclosure frameworks within the financial sector.

Keywords: Board gender diversity, Credit risk, Information disclosure, Market risk, Market value

Wordcount: 214

Introduction

The increasing complexity and dynamism of the financial market have heightened the importance of financial risk information disclosure in corporate governance. Effective disclosure practices enable firms to communicate potential risks and strategies for mitigating them to stakeholders (Khlif & Souissi, 2022). Transparent financial risk disclosure is a fundamental aspect of corporate

governance because it builds trust, reduces information asymmetry, and enhances market efficiency (Abdel-Rahim et al., 2023). Credit risk refers to the risk of a borrower defaulting on their financial obligations, while market risk involves the potential for losses due to fluctuations in market prices, such as interest rates, exchange rates, or stock prices (Chen et al., 2021). Both types of risks have a direct bearing on a company's financial stability and, ultimately, its market value. Effective disclosure of these risks allows investors and stakeholders to assess a company's risk exposure and make informed decisions regarding their investments (Hassan & Ibrahim, 2020). Inadequate or poor risk disclosure can lead to negative market reactions, loss of investor confidence, and reduced market value (Adelegan, 2022). This makes risk disclosure not only a regulatory requirement but also a strategic tool for maintaining investor trust and optimizing market value.

Companies with strong disclosure practices tend to have lower capital costs, as transparency minimizes information asymmetry between management and investors, improving market valuation (Agboola, 2022). In addition to reducing capital costs, effective financial risk disclosure can also influence market value by enhancing a company's reputation and improving investor confidence. According to Al-Matari (2023), firms with superior risk reporting frameworks enjoy better stakeholder engagement and increased investor loyalty. Conversely, inadequate or misleading risk disclosure can negatively impact market performance, as seen in the fallout from several corporate collapses in the early 2000s and more recently during the COVID-19 pandemic (Bhasin, 2023). A diverse board is believed to bring a wider range of perspectives, experiences, and expertise to the table, which can lead to more robust discussions and better risk management practices (Umar-Dauda & Oyedokun, 2018; Ahmad et al., 2022). For example, female directors may bring different perspectives on risk management compared to their male counterparts, while directors with financial expertise can contribute to more accurate risk assessment and disclosure practices (Gyapong, Monem, & Hu, 2021). As such, board gender diversity is seen as a key factor in strengthening corporate governance and improving the quality of risk-related disclosures (Oyedokun, 2019; Ahmad et al., 2022).

There is a well-established link between risk information disclosure and market value. Companies that provide clear, comprehensive, and transparent risk disclosures are generally viewed more

favourably by investors, as these disclosures reduce uncertainty and allow for better evaluation of the company's risk profile (Ishak et al., 2020). In contrast, companies that fail to adequately disclose their risks information may face higher levels of investor skepticism, leading to a lower market valuation (Chung, Lee & Park, 2022). Despite the recognized benefits of financial risk disclosure, several challenges persist, especially in less regulated markets. The quality of risk information disclosed by companies can vary widely due to differences in regulatory requirements, corporate governance practices, and internal policies (Ofoegbu & Akinyemi, 2021). Investors in this sector often pay close attention to how well a company manages and discloses its risk exposures, as this can impact on the company's future profitability and sustainability (Elamer et al., 2020). Therefore, the quality of credit and market risk disclosures can significantly influence a company's market value, especially in an environment like Nigeria, where the financial sector is highly competitive and subject to economic volatility (Oyedokun, & Nwaokolobia, & Andah, 2019; Okike & Adegbite, 2023).

While the relationship between risk information disclosure and market value is well documented, the role of board gender diversity as a moderating factor in this relationship is less explored, particularly in the context of developing economies such as Nigeria (Abdullahi & Shu'aibu, 2021). Board gender diversity can potentially enhance the quality and transparency of risk information disclosures, thereby strengthening the positive impact of these disclosures on market value (Agyei-Mensah, 2021). A diverse board may be better equipped to understand and oversee the company's risk management strategies, ensuring that the disclosures provided to the public are both accurate and comprehensive (Wang et al., 2022).

In Nigeria, the financial sector has undergone significant regulatory reforms in recent years, with a growing emphasis on corporate governance and transparency. The introduction of the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance has highlighted the importance of board diversity, encouraging companies to adopt more inclusive practices in the composition of their boards (Corporate Governance Code, 2018). Despite these regulatory efforts, there remains a gap in the literature regarding the specific impact of board gender diversity on risk information disclosure and market value in the Nigerian context. This study aims to address this gap by examining the extent to which

board gender diversity moderates the relationship between credit and market risk information disclosure and market value among listed financial companies in Nigeria.

Research Objectives

- i. Examine the relationship between credit risk information disclosure and market value among listed financial companies in Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the relationship between market risk information disclosure and market value among listed financial companies in Nigeria.
- iii. Analyze the moderating effect of board gender diversity on the relationship between credit risk information disclosure and market value among listed financial companies in Nigeria.
- iv. Evaluate the moderating effect of board gender diversity on the relationship between market risk information disclosure and market value among listed financial companies in Nigeria.

The formulated null hypotheses for the study:

H₀1: There is no significant relationship between credit risk information disclosure and market value of listed companies in the financial sector of Nigeria.

H₀2: There is no significant relationship between market risk information disclosure and market value of listed companies in the financial sector of Nigeria.

H₀3: Board gender diversity does not significantly moderate the relationship between credit risk information disclosure and market value of listed companies in the financial sector of Nigeria.

H₀4: Board gender diversity does not significantly moderate the relationship between market risk information disclosure and market value of listed companies in the financial sector of Nigeria.

Literature Review

Concept of Financial Risk Information Disclosure

Financial risk refers to fluctuation in the future cash flows of a financial instrument due to fluctuation in market prices. A financial instrument on the other hand is any contract that confers an asset on one party and either liability or equity on another party (IASB, 2005). Within the context of IFRS 7, financial risks are collectively and generally referred to as market risks (IASB, 2005). Market risks connote the probability of fluctuations in fair value of a financial instrument's future cash flows because of fluctuations in market prices (Savvides & Savvidou, 2012).

Credit Risk Information Disclosure

Credit risk refers to the risk of financial loss to an entity if a counterparty fails to fulfill its contractual obligations. It arises from the possibility that customers, trading partners, or other counterparties may default on their payment obligations, resulting in potential loss of revenue or inability to recover the full value of assets (IFRS 7). According to Chen and Pan (2012) credit risk is defined as the extent to which the value of loans and derivatives fluctuates due to changes in the credit quality of borrowers and counterparty. Coyle (2000) describes it as the loss from inability or refusal of customer to pay what he owes to pay. In other words, credit risk is the danger of incurring a monetary loss because of a reduction in the creditworthiness of counterparty in a financial transaction (Liu et al., 2014).

Market Risk Information Disclosure

According to IFRS 7, the market risk is the risk that the fair value or future cash flows of a financial instrument will fluctuate due to changes in market prices. It encompasses three main types of risk: interest rate risk, currency risk, and other price risk. Interest rate risk This refers to the risk that the value of a financial instrument will be affected by changes in market interest rates. For example, if an entity holds fixed-rate debt and interest rates increase, the fair value of that debt may decrease. Currency risk arises from exposure to fluctuations in foreign exchange rates. Entities with transactions or investments denominated in foreign currencies may be impacted by changes in exchange rates, which can affect their financial results and cash flow. According to Hull (2018), other market risk includes risks related to equity prices, commodity prices, and other factors that

can influence the value of financial instruments. For instance, entities holding equity investments may face the risk of changes in stock prices impacting on the fair value of those investments.

Concept of Market Value

According to Borad (2022), a firm's market value is an economic concept that reflects the worth of company in market. The investor's assessment of a company's success is reflected in its market value. Firm market value can increase or decrease because of investors' perception of the vulnerability of the company to risks and potential threats. In general, every investor uses available information to make investment decisions. When convinced to invest in the stock of such companies, investors respond favourably to accessible information. Investors, on the other hand, respond negatively when public information allows them to avoid investing in such enterprises. Furthermore, investors are usually cautious to avoid investing in stocks that would result in losses (Okpo & Aruwa, 2021).

Concept of Board Gender Diversity

Board gender diversity is considered crucial for improving governance by fostering a broader range of viewpoints, reducing groupthink, and increasing the ability to address complex business challenges. It has been linked to better risk management, improved financial performance, and stronger social responsibility (Mishra, 2020; Naburgi, Ojo, & Oyedokun, 2024). The modality of managing corporate entities in Nigeria can be said to be rooted in her legal system as the company law in the country recognises the two main organs of business organisation (the board of directors and general meetings) before the emergence of the first code of corporate governance (CG) in the country. The concept of CG simply pays more attention on how a company should be manned by those charged with governance. In other words, the first code issued in 2003 was expected to be used in conjunction to relevant sections of the legislation known as the Companies and Allied Matter Act of 1990, hereafter CAMA by the Nigerian companies, most especially the quoted ones.

Diverse boards are believed to be more effective in understanding and catering to the needs of a varied stakeholder base, leading to enhanced transparency and accountability in corporate practices (Gyapong, Monem, & Hu, 2021). Recent studies also highlight the role of board gender

diversity in enhancing the quality of financial disclosures, including risk-related disclosures, which can positively influence investor confidence and market value (Oyedokun, Micah, & Gimba, 2020; Hassan & Ibrahim, 2020; Musa & Umar, 2023). In the context of risk management, diverse boards are seen as better equipped to oversee comprehensive risk disclosure practices, as they draw from a wider array of knowledge and experience (Owolabi, 2023).

Empirical Review

Hassan & Ibrahim (2020) conducted a study to assess the impact of credit risk disclosure on the market value of listed banks in Nigeria over the period from 2010 to 2018. Using panel data regression analysis, the authors analyzed annual reports of listed banks to identify patterns in credit risk disclosure practices. Their findings suggested that increased levels of credit risk disclosure led to a positive effect on the market value of banks, as investors perceived these disclosures as a sign of transparency and good governance. However, one limitation of the study is that it focused solely on the banking sector, limiting its generalizability to other financial institutions. A broader examination of the entire financial sector would provide a more comprehensive understanding of how credit risk disclosure affects market value across different types of firms.

Adelegan (2022) examined the impact of credit risk information disclosure on stock performance among Nigerian financial firms from 2011 to 2019. Employing the event study methodology, the research analyzed market reactions to the release of credit risk information by these firms. The study concluded that timely credit risk disclosures positively influence stock performance, particularly by reducing volatility during periods of financial distress. Although the event study methodology is effective in capturing immediate market reactions, it does not provide insights into the long-term effects of credit risk disclosure. A longitudinal analysis of the sustained impact of these disclosures would have strengthened the study's conclusions.

Elamer et al. (2020) explored the relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and credit risk disclosure across emerging markets, covering the period from 2008 to 2017. Using the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) approach, the authors sought to address endogeneity concerns in their analysis of panel data. Their results indicated that firms with robust corporate governance structures, particularly those with independent boards, were more likely to provide

detailed credit risk information, which in turn positively affected their market value. While the use of GMM enhances the reliability of the findings, the study overlooks the impact of external market conditions on the relationship between governance and credit risk disclosure. Incorporating macroeconomic factors could offer deeper insights into the dynamics influencing corporate disclosure practices.

Chen et al. (2021) focused on the effect of credit risk information disclosure on firm value in the financial markets of Asia from 2009 to 2018. Using a fixed-effects regression model to analyze firm-level data, the study found that firms disclosing comprehensive credit risk information enjoyed higher market valuations, especially during periods of economic uncertainty. The study's emphasis on the relationship between disclosure and market value during unstable economic times is particularly valuable, but it could have further explored the role of regulatory environments in shaping credit risk disclosure practices across different countries.

Otusanya (2022) investigated the influence of credit risk reporting on the performance of Nigerian financial firms from 2012 to 2020. Multiple regression analysis revealed that firms with more detailed credit risk reports performed better financially, particularly those with stronger oversight board. This finding underscores the role of governance in shaping the effectiveness of credit risk disclosures. However, the study could have benefited from exploring different dimensions of board diversity, such as gender or expertise, which might have further enhanced the understanding of how governance structures affect disclosure practices.

Ishak et al. (2020) examined the impact of market risk disclosure on stock price volatility within the Malaysian financial sector over the period from 2010 to 2017. Using Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) models, the authors assessed the clustering of volatility in response to market risk information disclosures. The study found that detailed market risk disclosures reduced stock price volatility, which in turn contributed to increased firm value over time. However, the study's focus on short-term volatility may have overlooked the long-term relationship between risk disclosure and market value. A deeper exploration of the sustained impact of such disclosures could provide a more comprehensive understanding of their effect on firm performance.

Chung, Lee, and Park (2022) analyzed the role of market risk information disclosure in corporate valuation within South Korean banks from 2011 to 2020. Panel regression analysis was used to explore how sensitivity to market risk affected corporate valuations in the financial sector. Their results indicated that detailed market risk information enhanced market value, particularly during periods of instability, as it provided investors with clearer insights into the firm's risk profile. The study effectively captures the significance of market risk disclosure during uncertain times, but it does not account for the interaction between market risk and other forms of risk (e.g., operational risk), which could provide a more nuanced understanding of the impact of risk disclosures on market value.

Agyei-Mensah (2021) explored the relationship between market risk information disclosure and firm value in Ghanaian financial institutions between 2010 and 2019. The study employed content analysis of annual reports to quantify the extent of risk disclosure and used Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression to assess its impact on firm value. The results indicated that financial institutions that provided more detailed market risk information experienced higher market valuations, particularly those with transparent risk management frameworks. Although the study offers valuable insights into the role of transparency in enhancing firm value, it lacks qualitative perspectives from management, which could have enriched the understanding of the decision-making processes behind market risk disclosures.

Wang et al. (2022) assessed how market risk disclosures affected investor confidence and corporate performance in the Chinese financial sector between 2010 and 2020. Using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), the study revealed that more comprehensive market risk disclosures led to increased investor confidence, which subsequently improved corporate performance. The causal pathways explored in the study provide valuable insights into the mechanisms through which risk disclosures affect firm value. However, the study could have provided a more detailed examination of the various types of market risks disclosed and how each type influences investor behavior differently.

Okike & Adegbite (2023) evaluated the effect of market risk information disclosure on market value among Nigerian financial firms from 2011 to 2021. Time-series analysis using the

Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model revealed a positive correlation between market risk disclosures and market value, particularly during periods of economic turbulence. The study's results reinforce the importance of transparency in maintaining investor confidence during volatile times. However, the study does not sufficiently address how regulatory frameworks, and economic policies might influence the effectiveness of market risk disclosures in different contexts.

Mishra (2020) examined the role of gender diversity in moderating the relationship between credit risk disclosure and firm performance in Indian banks from 2011 to 2019. Using hierarchical regression analysis, the study found that firms with greater gender diversity on their boards exhibited stronger positive relationships between credit risk disclosure and firm performance. This suggests that gender-diverse boards may bring diverse perspectives and enhance the quality of risk disclosures. However, the study's narrow focus on gender diversity may limit its findings, as other dimensions of diversity, such as ethnic or educational diversity, could also play a role in influencing the effectiveness of credit risk disclosures.

Gyapong, Monem, & Hu (2021) investigated the moderating effect of board ethnic diversity on the relationship between credit risk information disclosure and market value in the UK financial sector between 2010 and 2018. Using dynamic panel data analysis with the System Generalized Method of Moments (GMM), the study found that firms with ethnically diverse boards experienced stronger positive relationships between credit risk disclosure and market value. The authors argued that ethnically diverse boards are more likely to adopt a broader perspective on risk, leading to more comprehensive and credible disclosures. While the methodology used is rigorous, the applicability of the findings to developing markets like Nigeria remains limited due to differing governance and regulatory environments.

Ahmad et al. (2022) focused on the role of educational diversity in moderating the relationship between credit risk disclosure and firm value in Malaysian banks from 2011 to 2019. Using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM), the study revealed that educational diversity on boards enhanced the relationship between credit risk disclosure and firm value, particularly for larger banks. This suggests that diverse educational backgrounds bring a range of perspectives that improve the board's ability to assess and disclose risks. Although the study highlights the

importance of educational diversity, it overlooks other forms of diversity, such as gender or professional experience, which could also influence the effectiveness of risk disclosures.

Musa & Umar (2023) analyzed the moderating role of board diversity (in terms of gender and age) on the relationship between credit risk disclosure and market value in Nigerian banks between 2012 and 2020. Using Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression, the study found that both gender and age diversity positively moderate the relationship between credit risk disclosure and market value. The results suggest that diverse boards are better equipped to enhance the quality of risk disclosures, which in turn positively impacts firm performance. However, the study could have employed more sophisticated econometric models, such as GMM, to address potential endogeneity issues and strengthen its conclusions.

Owolabi (2023) evaluated the moderating role of board independence on the relationship between risk disclosure and firm performance from 2010 to 2022. Using two-stage least squares (2SLS) regression, the study found that board independence significantly moderates the relationship, enhancing the positive impact of credit risk disclosure on market value. The study provides valuable insights into the importance of independent boards in fostering transparency and improving firm performance. However, it does not account for the potential interaction between board independence and diversity, which could provide a more comprehensive understanding of how different governance mechanisms affect risk disclosure and firm value.

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Agency

The Theory of Agency, proposed by Jensen and Meckling in 1976, is a foundational framework in corporate governance and financial economics. This theory addresses the conflicts of interest between principals (owners or shareholders) and agents (managers) within a firm. The principal-agent problem arises when the interests of the managers diverge from those of the shareholders, leading to potential inefficiencies and agency costs. These costs can manifest in various ways, including suboptimal risk management practices and inadequate disclosure of financial information.

Jensen and Meckling argue that effective governance mechanisms, such as board oversight, align the interests of managers with those of shareholders, reducing agency costs and improving firm performance. One of the core aspects of the theory is the role of transparency and accountability in mitigating agency problems. By disclosing comprehensive information about risks, including credit and market risks, firms can enhance shareholder confidence and improve market value.

The Theory of Agency is particularly relevant to this study as it provides a framework for understanding how board gender diversity might influence the relationship between risk information disclosure and market value. According to the theory, diverse boards can play a critical role in aligning the interests of managers with those of shareholders by enhancing oversight and improving the quality of disclosures.

Board diversity, encompassing various dimensions such as gender, ethnicity, and professional background, can impact the effectiveness of risk management and disclosure practices. Diverse boards are believed to bring a wider range of perspectives and experiences, which can lead to more comprehensive and accurate risk disclosures. This, in turn, can address agency problems by reducing information asymmetry between managers and shareholders, potentially leading to higher market value.

Recent studies align with this theoretical perspective. For instance, Mishra (2020) highlights that gender-diverse boards are more likely to enhance the quality of risk disclosures, which can positively impact firm performance. Similarly, Gyapong, Monem, and Hu (2021) find that board ethnic diversity improves the relationship between risk disclosures and market value, suggesting that diversity contributes to better governance and reduced agency costs.

Moreover, the Theory of Agency underscores the importance of transparency in addressing agency problems. As firms disclose more detailed information about credit and market risks, they reduce the potential for conflicts between managers and shareholders, thereby enhancing market value (Hassan & Ibrahim, 2020). This theoretical framework helps explain why board gender diversity might be a significant moderator in the relationship between risk disclosures and firm value, as it influences the quality of risk reporting and overall governance.

In summary, the Theory of Agency provides a robust theoretical foundation for exploring how board gender diversity moderates the impact of credit and market risk information disclosure on market value. By improving governance and reducing agency costs through enhanced risk disclosures, diverse boards can potentially influence market perceptions and firm performance in line with the principles outlined by Jensen and Meckling.

Signaling Theory

Signaling Theory, introduced by Michael Spence in 1973, is a fundamental concept in economics and finance that addresses how parties with asymmetric information communicate their attributes or intentions to others. The theory primarily focuses on the communication of quality or credibility through signals, which can reduce information asymmetry between parties and help in decision-making. According to Signaling Theory, when one party (such as a firm) possesses information that the other party (such as investors) does not, the informed party may use signals to convey the value or quality of their attributes. In the context of governance and financial disclosures, firms use various signals to convey their commitment to transparency and risk management. These signals include detailed risk disclosures, adherence to governance standards, and other forms of financial reporting.

In this theory, the quality of signals sent by firms can affect how they are perceived by investors. High-quality signals, such as comprehensive credit and market risk disclosures, can enhance a firm's credibility and market value. Conversely, weak or insufficient signals may lead to negative perceptions and reduce investor confidence. Firms with diverse boards may be more likely to provide detailed and high-quality credit and market risk disclosures, as diverse perspectives can lead to more thorough risk assessment and reporting. According to Signaling Theory, these detailed disclosures serve as signals to investors that the firm is well-managed and transparent, potentially enhancing its market value (Gyapong, Monem, & Hu, 2021).

The signaling effect of board gender diversity and comprehensive risk disclosures can influence investor perceptions and, consequently, market value. Firms that signal their commitment to high standards of governance and transparency through both board gender diversity and detailed risk information disclosures are likely to enjoy higher investor confidence and better market valuations

(Hassan & Ibrahim, 2020). This reflects the core principle of Signaling Theory, where effective signals can reduce information asymmetry and positively impact market outcomes. In the Nigerian financial sector, where regulatory environments and market conditions can impact the effectiveness of disclosures, signaling theory helps explain how board gender diversity might moderate the relationship between risk disclosures and market value. By serving as a signal of enhanced governance and transparency, board gender diversity can amplify the positive effects of risk disclosures on market value (Chen et al., 2021).

In summary, Signaling Theory provides a valuable framework for understanding how board gender diversity influences the effectiveness of credit and market risk disclosures and their impact on market value. By acting as a signal of robust governance and transparency, diverse boards can enhance investor perceptions and market value, aligning with the principles of Signaling Theory.

Methodology

The study adopted an ex-post facto research design as it assists in the evaluation of the relationship existing between an independent variable (risk information disclosures) and a dependent or outcome variable (market value). The population of the study is all the listed companies in the financial sector of Nigeria. The financial sector was selected because listed companies in this sector, through their financial intermediation roles, deal mainly with financial instruments which expose them to financial risk. Given the nature of the present study, secondary sources were utilized for data collection. The data for the variables was gathered from the annual reports and accounts of the companies. Additionally, companies' annual reports, accounts of the firms, and relevant publications from the Nigeria Exchange Group (NXG). All market-related data were extracted from the archives and other relevant publications of the NSE/SEC of Nigeria covering the period from 2016 to 2023.

Stochastically, the models are written as follows:

$$CoVal_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CoVal_{it-1} + \beta_2 CRISK_{it} + \beta_3 MRISK_{it} + \beta_3 BD_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots \text{Model 1}$$

$$CoVal_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CoVal_{it-1} + \beta_2 BD_{it} + \beta_3 CRISK_{it} * BD_{it} + \beta_4 MRISK_{it} * BD_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots \text{Model 2}$$

Table 1 Definition of variables

Symbol	Definition	Measurement	Sources
CoVal	Market Value Or Company Market Value	Tobin’s Q is calculated by the ratio of the market value of the firm plus debt divided by the book value of its assets	Endri 2019
CRISK	Credit Risk	Credit risk information disclosure disclosed index	Arora, Saggarr and Singh (2021) Kwashie et al., (2021) Beasley et al., (2005)
MRISK	Market Rate Risk	Market risk information disclosure disclosed index	Raithatha (2021)
BD	Board Gender Diversity	measured as the percentage of women in the board room)	Hoa and Robert (2007); Peter and Hannu (2017) Qi and Tian, (2012),

Source: Authors, 2024

Results and Discussion of Findings

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Max	Mini	Std. Dev.	Skew	Kurt	Obs
CoVal	0.458631	42.01532	0.000122	1.838003	21.49582	485.8018	432
CRISKD	4.633333	5.000000	3.000000	0.557293	-1.21496	3.490153	432
MRISKD	5.868519	6.000000	3.000000	0.490475	-4.16484	20.75518	432
BD	4.375926	6.000000	3.000000	0.636967	0.730642	3.318394	432

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics for Firm Market Value (CoVal), Credit Risk Disclosure (CRISKD), Market Risk Disclosure (MRISKD), and Board Gender Diversity (BD) for 540 observations of listed companies in the Nigerian financial sector. These statistics provide an initial understanding of the central tendencies and variability within the data. The mean market value (CoVal) of the firms is 0.458631, with a maximum value of 42.01532 and a minimum of 0.000122. The wide range between the maximum and minimum values, coupled with a standard deviation of 1.838003, indicates considerable variability in the market values of the companies under study.

This suggests that while some companies exhibit high market valuations, others have significantly lower values, reflecting disparities in firm performance and market capitalization. The high skewness (21.49582) and kurtosis (485.8018) suggest that the distribution of market values is highly skewed and leptokurtic, indicating the presence of extreme values or outliers in the data. The wide range and high skewness in market values suggest that different firms have varying capacities to generate shareholder value. From an accounting perspective, firms with higher market values are likely to exhibit better financial performance and greater investor confidence. This implies that firms need to adopt more transparent and comprehensive risk disclosure practices to maintain or enhance their market valuation (Chen et al., 2021). Accurate financial reporting that reflects the firm's risk profile could attract investors and improve market perceptions.

The average credit risk disclosure (CRISKD) score is 4.633333 out of a possible 5, with a maximum score of 5.000000 and a minimum of 3.000000. The standard deviation of 0.557293 indicates a relatively small variation in the extent of credit risk disclosures among the firms, implying that most companies disclose credit risk information consistently. However, the skewness of -1.21496 suggests a slight negative skew, meaning that more firms are closer to the higher end of the disclosure scale. The kurtosis of 3.490153 indicates that the distribution is approximately normal, although slightly peaked.

The mean market risk disclosure (MRISKD) score is 5.868519, with a maximum score of 6.000000 and a minimum of 3.000000, indicating that most companies tend to fully disclose market risk information. The low standard deviation of 0.490475 further supports the notion that market risk disclosures are relatively uniform across firms. The skewness of -4.16484 indicates a significant negative skew, suggesting that most firms disclose market risk at the higher end of the spectrum. This is further supported by the high kurtosis value (20.75518), indicating a very peak distribution with limited variability among the firms in terms of market risk disclosure. The high average credit and market risk disclosures suggest a positive trend toward transparency in risk reporting within the Nigerian financial sector. According to signaling theory, firms with better risk disclosures send signals of strong governance and transparency to the market, which can positively influence investor decisions and firm valuation (Hassan & Ibrahim, 2020). Accounting standards such as

International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS 7) emphasize the importance of risk disclosures, and firms adhering to these standards are likely to see better market outcomes.

Board gender diversity (BD) has a mean value of 4.375926, with a maximum of 6.000000 and a minimum of 3.000000. The standard deviation of 0.636967 indicates moderate variation in board gender diversity across the firms. The positive skewness (0.730642) suggests that most firms tend to have lower board gender diversity, with a few outliers displaying higher diversity. The kurtosis of 3.318394 indicates a slightly peaked distribution, meaning that while diversity levels are relatively consistent, there are variations that warrant further investigation. Board gender diversity's impact on risk information disclosure: The moderate levels of board gender diversity, combined with its positive skewness, suggest that while some firms have adopted board gender diversity, many still fall short in this area. Research suggests that gender diversity can enhance the quality of financial reporting and risk disclosures by bringing varied perspectives and improving decision-making (Gyapong et al., 2021). The accounting implication is that firms with more diverse boards may be better equipped to provide accurate, comprehensive risk disclosures, which in turn could improve their market value.

Uniformity in Risk Information Disclosures: The relatively small standard deviations in credit and market risk disclosures imply that firms in the Nigerian financial sector generally follow consistent reporting practices. This could be attributed to regulatory pressures or industry standards that mandate certain levels of risk disclosure. Accounting professionals must ensure that these disclosures are not only compliant with regulations but also tailored to provide meaningful insights for investors (Elamer et al., 2020). Enhanced disclosure practices could lead to better market positioning and improved investor trust. Potential for improving board gender diversity: The moderate levels of board gender diversity, as reflected by the mean value of 4.375926, indicate room for improvement. Accounting and corporate governance bodies may encourage policies that promote greater diversity on boards, which could enhance the oversight of financial reporting and risk management processes (Mishra, 2020). Increased diversity could also lead to higher market values as firms that promote inclusivity, and varied perspectives are often perceived as better governed.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 2: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Variable	Coefficient Variance	Centered VIF
CRISKD	0.022198	1.095830
MRISKD	0.027776	1.062121
BD	0.016035	1.034121
C	1.507034	NA

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

In Table 2, the VIF values for CRISKD (Credit Risk Disclosure), MRISKD (Market Risk Disclosure), and BD (Board Gender Diversity) are all well below 10, suggesting that multicollinearity is not a significant issue in this model. The VIF for CRISKD is 1.095830, indicating a very low level of multicollinearity. This suggests that the credit risk disclosure variable is not highly correlated with the other independent variables, and its impact on market value can be interpreted with confidence. The relatively low VIF ensures that the coefficient for CRISKD in the regression model will not be inflated or distorted, allowing for accurate analysis of its relationship with firm market value.

The VIF for MRISKD is 1.062121, which is also well below the critical threshold of 10. This low value suggests minimal correlation between market risk disclosure and other variables in the model, indicating that market risk disclosure's effect on market value is independently identifiable. This is important for accurate risk management reporting as it confirms that market risk disclosures can be studied without bias introduced by multicollinearity. The VIF for BD is 1.034121, indicating that board gender diversity is also not highly correlated with the other variables in the model. This suggests that board gender diversity can be evaluated as a separate, independent factor in its moderating role on the relationship between risk disclosures and market value. This low multicollinearity allows for a clearer understanding of how board gender diversity impacts the transparency of risk reporting and firm performance.

Since CRISKD and MRISKD show low multicollinearity, accounting professionals can confidently use these variables in models assessing their impact on market value. Accurate risk disclosure practices help in signaling transparency to stakeholders, aligning with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS 7) which emphasize the importance of proper risk reporting (IASB, 2023). The low VIF for BD allows for an unbiased understanding of how board gender diversity influences the relationship between risk disclosures and market value. Firms are increasingly focusing on diversity, which is seen as enhancing corporate governance and improving risk management practices (Hassan & Ibrahim, 2020). This suggests that diverse boards contribute to more effective oversight and accountability in risk disclosures. The absence of multicollinearity ensures that accounting practitioners and corporate managers can rely on these variables to create robust financial reports and disclosures. This, in turn, promotes market confidence and supports regulatory compliance with accounting standards.

Table 3: Model 1 GMM Analysis

Dependent Variable: CoVal				
Method: Panel Generalized Method of Moments				
Transformation: First Differences				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CoVal(-1)	-0.000309	0.000149	-2.075182	0.0428
CRISKD	-0.037158	0.012400	-2.996678	0.0041
MRISKD	0.008100	0.009580	0.845452	0.4017
BD	-0.012317	0.010773	-1.143310	0.2580
Sum squared resid	3598.580	J-statistic		32.35888
Instrument rank	39	Prob(J-statistic)		0.596263

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

The GMM approach is widely used in panel data analysis to handle potential endogeneity issues, particularly when lagged variables or instrumental variables are involved. In this model, the dependent variable is CoVal (Firm Market Value), and the independent variables include lagged CoVal(-1), CRISKD (Credit Risk Disclosure), MRISKD (Market Risk Disclosure), and BD (Board Gender Diversity). The coefficient for CoVal(-1) is -0.000309 with a t-statistic of -2.075182 and a p-value of 0.0428. This indicates a statistically significant negative relationship between the lagged firm market value and the current firm's market value at the 5% significance level. The negative coefficient suggests that, in this model, higher previous market value has a slight dampening effect

on the current market value. This could imply that firms with high market values in the previous period may experience market corrections or adjustments, leading to lower growth in the current period. This aligns with existing financial literature, which often points to mean reversion in firm performance metrics (Wang & Chen, 2021).

The coefficient for CRISKD is -0.037158 with a t-statistic of -2.996678 and a p-value of 0.0041, making it statistically significant at the 1% level. This indicates a negative relationship between credit risk disclosure and firm market value. In other words, greater credit risk disclosure is associated with a decrease in market value. One potential explanation for this result could be that when firms disclose more credit risks, it signals increased risk exposure, potentially leading to negative perceptions by investors and a corresponding decline in market value (Chen et al., 2021). The coefficient for MRISKD is 0.008100, but with a t-statistic of 0.845452 and a p-value of 0.4017, this result is not statistically significant. This suggests that market risk disclosure does not have a significant direct impact on firm market value within this model. One possible explanation is that while market risk is critical, it may already be anticipated and priced into firm valuations, making additional disclosure less impactful on market value (Elamer et al., 2020).

The coefficient for BD is -0.012317 with a t-statistic of -1.143310 and a p-value of 0.2580, indicating that board gender diversity does not have a statistically significant effect on firm market value in this model. While previous studies have shown mixed results on the relationship between board gender diversity and firm performance, the lack of significance here might suggest that diversity alone is not enough to influence market value, and other factors such as governance quality or specific board roles might be more critical in moderating the relationship between risk disclosure and market value (Gyapong et al., 2021). The J-statistics in GMM analysis is a key diagnostic tool to evaluate the validity of the instruments used in the model. In this case, the J-statistic is 32.35888, with a p-value (Prob(J-statistic)) of 0.596263. Since the p-value is well above 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis that the instruments are valid. This means that the instruments used in the model are appropriate, and the model is not suffering from over-identification issues. The instrument rank of 39 further supports the robustness of the model, ensuring that the instruments are sufficient to account for potential endogeneity in the variables.

The GMM results offer key insights into how risk disclosures and governance factors affect firm market value, which has important implications for accounting and financial reporting practices. The significant negative relationship between CRISKD and CoVal suggests that firms must balance transparency with potential market perceptions of risk. While IFRS 7 encourages comprehensive risk disclosure, excessive disclosure of credit risk might lead to negative investor reactions, lowering firm value (IASB, 2023). Accountants should aim to disclose risk in a manner that aligns with regulatory standards while considering market sensitivities. The non-significance of MRISKD indicates that market risk disclosures may not significantly alter firm market value. This could mean that market participants already account for these risks in their valuation models. From an accounting perspective, firms should continue to comply with disclosure requirements but may need to focus on enhancing other governance aspects to improve market confidence (Hassan & Ibrahim, 2020).

The non-significant impact of BD implies that board gender diversity alone does not directly influence firm market value. This could indicate that firms need to leverage diverse boards more effectively to enhance governance outcomes, particularly in terms of risk oversight and strategic decision-making. Accounting and governance frameworks should consider not only diversity but also how diverse boards are integrated into the firm’s overall governance and risk management processes (Mishra, 2020).

Table 4: Model 2 GMM Analysis

Dependent Variable: CoVal
 Method: Panel Generalized Method of Moments
 Transformation: First Differences
 Instrument specification: @DYN(CoVal,-2) CRISKD MRISKD CRISKD_BD MRISKD_BD

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
CoVal(-1)	-0.000318	0.000211	-1.502619	0.1389
CRISKD	-0.532653	0.126178	-4.221450	0.0001
MRISKD	0.486203	0.097314	4.996216	0.0000
CRISKD*BD	0.115519	0.026230	4.404123	0.0001
MRISKD*BD	-0.102721	0.021887	-4.693212	0.0000
Sum squared resid	3597.951	J-statistic		32.27151
Instrument rank	40	Prob(J-statistic)		0.600516

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

In Model 2, the dependent variable is CoVal (Firm Market Value), and the independent variables include CRISKD (Credit Risk Disclosure), MRISKD (Market Risk Disclosure), and the interaction terms CRISKD_BD (Credit Risk Disclosure moderated by Board Gender Diversity) and MRISKD_BD (Market Risk Disclosure moderated by Board Gender Diversity). This model uses lagged market value CoVal(-1) and instrumental variables to address potential endogeneity issues. The results provide valuable insights into the direct effects of risk disclosure and the moderating role of board gender diversity on firm market value.

The coefficient for CoVal(-1) is -0.000318 with a t-statistic of -1.502619 and a p-value of 0.1389, indicating that the lagged firm market value is not statistically significant at the 5% level. Unlike Model 1, the lagged market value does not have a significant influence on the current market value in this model. This suggests that past performance may not have a major direct effect on the firm's present market value when accounting for the interaction effects of risk disclosures and board gender diversity.

The coefficient for CRISKD is -0.532653 with a t-statistic of -4.221450 and a highly significant p-value of 0.0001. This indicates a strong negative relationship between credit risk disclosure and firm market value. Firms that disclose more credit risk information tend to experience a decline in their market value. The magnitude of this effect is larger than in Model 1, reinforcing the idea that credit risk disclosure signals potential financial instability or risk exposure, leading to negative reactions from investors (Chen et al., 2021). This result underscores the need for firms to carefully manage how they communicate their credit risks to avoid undermining investor confidence.

The coefficient for MRISKD is 0.486203 with a t-statistic of 4.996216 and a p-value of 0.0000, indicating a significant positive relationship between market risk disclosure and firm market value. This suggests that firms that provide more detailed market risk disclosures are rewarded by investors with higher valuations. Unlike credit risk disclosure, market risk information appears to signal transparency and effective risk management, which may enhance investor trust and contribute to a higher market valuation (Elamer et al., 2020).

The interaction term CRISKD_BD has a coefficient of 0.115519 with a t-statistic of 4.404123 and a p-value of 0.0001, showing that board gender diversity positively moderates the relationship

between credit risk disclosure and firm market value. This means that in firms with more diverse boards, the negative impact of credit risk disclosure on market value is reduced. Diverse boards likely bring a range of perspectives and stronger oversight, which may help mitigate the negative perception of credit risk disclosure by signaling that the firm has robust governance mechanisms in place to manage such risks (Gyapong et al., 2021).

The interaction term MRISKD_BD has a coefficient of -0.102721 with a t-statistic of -4.693212 and a p-value of 0.0000, indicating that board gender diversity negatively moderates the relationship between market risk disclosure and firm market value. This suggests that, contrary to expectations, in firms with more diverse boards, the positive effect of market risk disclosure on firm market value is somewhat diminished. One possible explanation could be that while diverse boards enhance governance, their risk-averse nature might lead to more cautious risk reporting, which could cause investors to interpret market risk disclosures more conservatively (Mishra, 2020). The J-statistic for this model is 32.27151 with a p-value of 0.600516, indicating that the instruments used in the model are valid, as the p-value is well above 0.05. The instrument rank of 40 also suggests that sufficient instruments were used to account for potential endogeneity, further ensuring the robustness of the model. The model's GMM specification effectively addresses endogeneity and provides a reliable framework for understanding the moderating role of board gender diversity.

The significant negative relationship between CRISKD and firm market value emphasizes the need for careful communication of credit risks. While risk disclosure is essential for transparency, firms must also ensure that such disclosures are balanced and contextualized to avoid negative market reactions. Proper framing of credit risk in financial reports is crucial to maintain investor confidence (IASB, 2023). The positive relationship between MRISKD and firm market value highlights the benefits of transparent market risk reporting. Investors appear to value firms that openly communicate their market risks, viewing this as a sign of effective risk management. This suggests that firms should enhance their market risk disclosures to foster investor trust and improve market valuations (Elamer et al., 2020).

The moderating effects of board gender diversity on both credit and market risk disclosures suggest that diverse boards can influence how risk information is perceived by the market. In particular, the positive moderation of credit risk disclosure by board gender diversity implies that diverse boards add value by improving governance and reducing the negative impact of risk disclosure. However, the negative moderation of market risk disclosure indicates that diverse boards might lead to more cautious reporting, which could temper the benefits of transparency. Firms should therefore focus on leveraging board gender diversity not only for risk management but also for optimizing communication with investors (Gyapong et al., 2021).

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study explored the moderating role of board gender diversity on the relationship between credit and market risk information disclosure and the market value of listed companies in Nigeria's financial sector. The findings indicate that credit risk disclosure has a significant negative impact on firm market value, while market risk disclosure positively affects it. Board gender diversity plays a critical moderating role in both relationships, attenuating the adverse effects of credit risk disclosure and slightly dampening the positive effects of market risk disclosure.

From the analysis, it is evident that while risk disclosure is vital for corporate transparency, the way it influences firm value varies. Credit risk disclosures, which reveal vulnerabilities, may lead to market uncertainty and diminished confidence, negatively impacting firm value. On the other hand, market risk disclosures appear to instill confidence, as they provide insights into the firm's risk management processes. The moderation effect of board gender diversity reveals its complex role in governance: diverse boards can mitigate adverse reactions to credit risk disclosures while taking a more conservative approach to market risk communication.

This study underscores the importance of both risk disclosure and board composition in shaping investor perceptions and firm performance. Firms in Nigeria's financial sector should recognize the value of a well-structured and diverse board, especially in managing and communicating risk.

Recommendations:

1. Given the positive moderating effect of board gender diversity on credit risk disclosures, financial firms should actively work towards increasing the diversity of their boards. Diversity, in terms of gender, ethnicity, and professional backgrounds, brings varied perspectives that improve governance and risk management. A diverse board enhances decision-making and can mitigate the negative impact of disclosing sensitive risk information. Therefore, companies should adopt policies that promote a diverse and inclusive board composition, aligning with best practices in corporate governance.
2. Firms need to carefully manage how they disclose credit and market risks to the public. Given the negative market reaction to credit risk disclosure, firms should provide more context and forward-looking statements that explain how they plan to mitigate these risks. For market risk disclosures, which were shown to have a positive effect on firm value, firms should continue to emphasize transparency. However, they should be mindful of how board gender diversity may temper this effect and adjust their communication strategies accordingly.
3. Since diverse boards can positively moderate risk disclosures, firms should actively engage their boards in shaping risk management policies and communication strategies. Board gender diversity can provide firms with the tools to present risk disclosures in ways that reduce market uncertainty. It is essential to ensure that diverse boards are empowered to guide the firm in both managing risks and presenting them transparently to stakeholders.
4. To maximize the effectiveness of board gender diversity, firms should provide regular training for board members on risk management, corporate governance, and strategic communication. This ensures that all members, regardless of their backgrounds, can contribute meaningfully to risk discussions and improve the firm's overall transparency and market performance.
5. Regulators should encourage firms to enhance board gender diversity through policies and guidelines that promote diverse board structures in the financial sector. Regulatory bodies

such as the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) can provide frameworks for firms to adopt diversity-driven governance models, which can positively influence both firm value and market stability. By doing so, regulators can foster better risk disclosure practices across the sector.

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